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Institutional implementation of Industry 4.0 competencies in TVET programmes in Indo-Pacific - critical success factors

Abstract

This paper questions: what are the critical success factors that support the implementation of Industry 4.0 competencies into TVET programme offerings? The scope of our study is programme offerings targeting STEM fields at the tertiary level across 15 countries in Indo-Pacific. The study evaluated the ‘actions already taken’; a survey questionnaire was used to collect data. The findings identified staff capacity development, supportive culture, availability of resources, and public awareness as critical success factors. In addition, TVET institution type and annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person boost the relationship. That is, TVET colleges are in a weaker position in implementations; countries with higher annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person have implemented more.

Keywords: 4th Industrial revolution, Asia, Indo-Pacific, Industry 4.0, Industry 4.0 competencies, South Asia, the Pacific, technical and vocational education and training, TVET

INTRODUCTION

Technical and vocational education and training (TVET) offers a combination of education, training, and skill development opportunities in a wide range of occupational fields, production processes, services, and livelihoods (ILO, 2020, p. 21). The pedagogical approach of TVET is a mix of theory, practice, and work-based learning leading to a qualification or other skill development options with a lifelong learning agenda at secondary, post-secondary, and tertiary levels. TVET institutions exercise the most influence and make the most contribution in incorporating qualifications and competencies into curricula, adopting appropriate teaching and learning practices, and capacity building of staff, which are amongst the core functions of a TVET system (The World Bank Group, 2021).

When TVET institutions achieving expectations, the incorporation of digital technologies tied to the fourth industrial revolution (commonly denoted as Industry 4.0) has become a necessity due to two main reasons. First, to succeed in the volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous (VUCA) world

that we currently live in (Millar et al., 2018), TVET institutions must increasingly rely on Industry 4.0 technologies. This led us to the second reason, i.e., Industry 4.0. Society has been experiencing dramatic transformations that are credited to Industry 4.0 digital technologies (World Economic Forum, 2016). In the context of work, Industry 4.0 technologies allow organisations to shift their operations in kind as required by the VUCA world creating smart workplaces. Shifting to Industry 4.0 technologies has become a part of national agendas, and the education sector, as a whole, should move forward with this agenda (The World Bank Group, 2021).

Building on the above context, we argue that the future of TVET is being shaped by Industry 4.0 technologies in two spheres. On the one hand, TVET should incorporate Industry 4.0 competencies into the curriculum of the existing as well as new programme offerings by defining learning objectives and mapping subject content to learning outcomes. Here, TVET teachers possessing the subject content expertise on Industry 4.0 technologies and an understanding of the competencies to be incorporated into the curriculum are the core, among other things. On the other hand, Industry 4.0 technologies have been making a profound impact on the digitalisation of pedagogies (Schröder, 2019; Spöttl and Windelband, 2021). Therefore, TVET should incorporate Industry 4.0 technologies into teaching, learning and assessment as well as teaching material development. Here, TVET teachers possessing digital skills to use Industry 4.0 technologies as well as possessing competencies to teach subject content with Industry 4.0 technologies are the core, among other things (The World Bank Group, 2021). The present study investigated 15 countries in Indo-Pacific. The literature from Indo-Pacific countries under study, on the one hand, suggests lack of supply of skilled manpower (e.g., Bhattacharyya and Mitra, 2020; Butt et al., 2020) and questions the quality of supply of skilled manpower by TVET institutions (e.g., Jabarullah and Hussain, 2019). On the other hand, highlights the challenges faced by TVET institutions such as financial and infrastructure (e.g., Gonçalves, 2019), teacher capabilities (e.g., Butt et al., 2020; Mahdum et al., 2019), and curriculum development (Butt et al., 2020). In addition, Gonçalves (2019) and Schröder (2019) suggest that challenges faced by TVET institutions are common to Asia as a whole.

In the above context, we question, what are the critical success factors that support the implementation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings? Accordingly, following the terminology introduced by UNESCO to be used worldwide uniformly (2021, p. 8), specifically, *qualifications*, *competencies*, and *implementation*, we investigated factors that support the successful implementation of competencies demanded by Industry 4.0 into programme offerings across 15 countries in Indo-Pacific, which are shown in Table 1. Annual growth rate of real gross domestic product per employed person is identified as useful in understanding country standings (Asian Development Bank, 2020, p. 49).

Table 1. Countries and characteristics

Country	Sample (% out of total responses) ¹	GDP growth ²
Bangladesh	10.75	5.9
Viet Nam	7	5.8
Myanmar	6.07	5.4
Cambodia	7	5.3
Mongolia	1.64	5.3
India	14.95	4.8
Nepal	4.44	3.9
Bhutan	3.98	3.4
Philippines	12.85	3.3
Papua New Guinea	1.64	3.0
Thailand	6.78	2.7
Malaysia	5.37	2.6
Sri Lanka	9.58	2.5
Fiji	1.17	1.7
Pakistan	6.78	1.1

Notes: ¹ = 428 (=100%); ² = Annual growth rate of real gross domestic product per employed person.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Implementation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

Responses of TVET institutions to Industry 4.0 inevitably move them toward digital transformation. Digital transformation involves digital adaptation, innovation, and acceleration (ILO, 2020, p. 25). With regard to digital adaptation, i.e., ‘how Industry 4.0 technology requires teaching new content’ (ILO, 2020, p. 25), literature emphasises the need of Industry 4.0 technologies becoming a part of TVET programme offerings (Bhattacharyya and Mitra, 2020; Butt et al., 2020; Schröder, 2019; Spöttl and Windelband, 2021). Industry expects, on the one hand, digital workflows currently in use to be reflected in programme offerings. On the other hand, with the continued digitisation of work processes, the industry requires workers to return to TVET institutions from time to time during their careers to remain relevant (ILO, 2020, p.60). This implies that TVET institutions must 1) update curricula and incorporate new content to the existing programmes, 2) introduce new programmes to fulfil requirements of new jobs, new occupations, and new industry/service sectors on a regular, continuous basis, and 3) introduce bridging programmes to reskill and upskill workers with the lifelong learning in mind. In doing so, forward-looking TVET systems must change their focus fourfold, namely, from academic pathways to applied learning pathways through internships for full-time courses, from classroom learning to work-based learning through work-study diploma pathways, from front-load learning to lifelong learning through accessible and bite-size programmes for upgrading, and from technical skills to multi-disciplinary skills through the integration of technical, transversal and citizenship skills.

With regard to digital innovation, i.e., ‘how Industry 4.0 technology enables new forms of teaching and learning’ (ILO, 2020, p. 25), Industry 4.0 technologies mediate knowledge in digital ways enriching the teaching and learning process (TVET Academy, 2021; ILO, 2020). Industry 4.0 technologies can make a complete shift to the traditional teaching and learning practices of TVET. Today, students are expected to learn theoretical aspects with the support of a variety of digital devices such as digitalised textbooks, smart boards/tables, and wearable gadgets or learn remotely through a

digital platform, still maintaining persistent learning by staying in near-constant contact with fellow students and teachers through mobile messaging apps (ILO, 2020). Students are expected to practice in a virtual reality-based training environment provided by the TVET institution or its industry partners. This way of teaching and learning is a complete shift from learning theory within the confine of a TVET institution’s classroom, practising within the confine of its workshop, and refining and mastering capabilities by engaging in a real assignment on the site of an industry partner.

When both mentioned above are taken together - teaching new content and using new forms of teaching and learning, a student may learn foundations through a TVET institution and obtain access to the labour market. He/she may continue to learn through options provided by the employer or higher educational institutions depending on the requirements of the job and his/her career aspirations. These learning events may be integrated into his/her job as microlearning, and he/she may engage in the learning using flexible learning avenues such as attending evening classes or using online/distance mode. Hence, Industry 4.0 technologies provide ample avenues for just-in-time learning. In the present study, by the term implementation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings we meant the extent to which institutions teach subject content by incorporating new content into existing programmes, introducing new programmes for newly emerged needs, introducing new programmes to reskill and upskill workers with lifelong learning in mind as well as use of digital technology-based delivery in teaching and learning.

Critical success factors

Given the importance of successful implementation of Industry 4.0 competencies, it is imperative for institutions embarking on the implementation to have a greater understanding of conditions that lead to success. Therefore, by the term critical success factors we meant the enabling conditions that are conducive to success in incorporating Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings. Building on the literature that will be reviewed in the below sections, the conceptual model shown in Figure 1 is developed for the study.

Figure 1. Research model

TVET staff capacity development

When materialising changes required by Industry 4.0, TVET staff possessing requisite capabilities is the key. UNESCO (2021) calls on its member countries to develop mechanisms to ensure TVET staff at all levels have opportunities to prepare for the profession and engage in continuing training and professional development. With regard to areas of staff capacity development, three types of knowledge - content, pedagogical, and technological are vital. That is, staff competencies should be at par with developments of Industry 4.0 technologies. However, recent literature (e.g., Butt et al., 2020; Holler et al., 2023; ILO, 2020; Mahdum et al., 2019) suggests that TVET staff do not have requisite knowledge, especially technological knowledge, and requisite level of digital competencies. This has a direct impact on the potential of incorporating Industry 4.0 competencies into TVET programme offerings. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H1: Staff capacity development enhances the incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

TVET supportive culture

The creation of a culture of innovation involving TVET staff at all levels (ILO, 2020), the promotion of exchanges among internal and external stakeholders (TVET Academy, 2021), the establishment of a multi-stakeholder collaboration system (Amegah, 2023; ILO, 2020; TVET Academy, 2021), and being open to change (ILO, 2020) were commonly identified as requisites for survival and growth of TVET institutions. Further, recent literature (e.g., Butt et al., 2020; Mahdum et al., 2019; The World Bank Group, 2021) suggests the value of providing support by TVET institutions for sharing of experiences on Industry 4.0 competencies and technologies. In addition, the literature suggests the importance of TVET institutions providing support to make changes to programme offerings (Alade and Windapo, 2020; The World Bank Group, 2021). Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H2: Supportive culture enhances the incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

TVET resources and public awareness

The availability of resources such as equipment, computer hardware, software and communication network for digital delivery, and the freedom to hire new staff with up-to-date competencies are vital requisites. In this regard, ILO (2020), TVET Academy (2021) and the World Bank Group (2021) emphasise the importance of TVET institutions having the ability to identify appropriate technological infrastructure as well as having autonomy to invest in such infrastructure. However, recent literature (e.g., Gonçalves, 2019; ILO, 2020; McGrath et al. 2020; Oketch 2016; The World Bank Group, 2021; TVET Academy, 2021) suggests that TVET institutions are experiencing financial and infrastructure shortages. The public awareness of Industry 4.0 technologies, changes to programme offerings, and academic pathways can also increase the demand for TVET programmes for beginner, intermediate or

advanced learners and for bridging programmes with the intention of upskilling and reskilling the workforce. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H3: The availability of resources and public awareness enhance the incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

Contextual factors

TVET institution type

TVET institutions are at the front line of programme delivery (UNESCO, 2021; World Economic Forum, 2016). The literature also suggests the existence of different types of TVET institutions such as universities, polytechnics, and colleges that involve in offering programmes in their entirety and/or their components (The World Bank Group, 2021; UNESCO-UNEVOC International Centre for TVET, 2020). These TVET institutions are expected to offer quality, relevant, and timely programmes addressing labour market demands. However, recent literature (e.g., ILO, 2020; Persson and Hermelin, 2018; UNESCO, 2021) suggests that TVET institutions' capacity to respond may vary by institution type. For example, ILO (2020, p.71) state 'in most countries – even in advanced economies – basic pedagogies, such as those enabled by distance learning or by digitally enhanced classrooms, have not yet been mainstreamed across the entire educational system'. Recent studies such as Bai and Paryono (2019), Marzuki et al. (2022), and Yaakob (2017) also provide evidence to suggest possible differences between TVET institutions in Indo-Pacific. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H4: Institution type enhances the incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

In line with Figure 1, following hypotheses are also proposed.

H4a: Institution type moderates the relationship between staff capacity development and the extent of incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

H4b: Institution type moderates the relationship between supportive culture and the extent of incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

H4c: Institution type moderates the relationship between the availability of resources and public awareness and the extent of incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

Annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person

A country's TVET system and its capacity to provide skilled labour are central components of the political economy. The design and development of the system of TVET could vary from country to country due to prevailing characteristics of the market economy and labour market relations. Further, a country's status in technological upgrading/innovation and economic growth and employment growth go hand in hand. Sustainable Development Goal 8 (SDG 8) propagates the importance of promoting

economic growth and labour productivity (The United Nations, n.d.). One of the targets of SGD8 is ‘achieving higher levels of economic productivity through diversification, technological upgrading, and innovation, including through a focus on high-value added and labour-intensive sectors’, which is depicted for each country by the indicator ‘annual growth rate of real gross domestic product (GDP) per employed person’ (identified as SDG8 - 8.2.1). This indicator conveys the idea of labour productivity.

The literature identifies an important connection between individuals participating in the labour market with tertiary education attainment (vocational and university) and a country’s annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person (Jongen, 2004; Marattin and Salotti, 2011). Bosler et al. (2019) referred this as labour quality and asserted the value of education attainment of those participate in the labour market. Jongen (2004) referred specifically to the importance of adult education and training and suggested an important connection between returns from training and education efforts and a country’s annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H5: Annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person enhances the incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

In line with Figure 1, following hypotheses are also proposed.

H5a: Annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person moderates the relationship between staff capacity development and the extent of incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

H5b: Annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person moderates the relationship between supportive culture and the extent of incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

H5c: Annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person moderates the relationship between the availability of resources and public awareness and the extent of incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

Overall, following hypotheses are proposed in line with Figure 1.

H6: Institution type and annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person moderate the relationship between staff capacity development and the extent of incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

H7: Institution type and annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person moderate the relationship between supportive culture and the extent of incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

H8: Institution type and annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person moderate the relationship between the availability of resources and public awareness and the extent of incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

METHODOLOGY

We collected data from 15 countries in Indo-Pacific using a survey questionnaire. The details of the measures used, sample, method of data collection, and methods of data analysis are presented in this section.

Measures

As shown in Figure 1, the study had three independent variables, one dependent variable and two moderators. All the measures used in the study are developed by the authors. Further, all the measures are on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree (strongly agree = 7, agree = 6, More or less agree = 5, moderate = 4, More or less disagree = 3, disagree = 2, strongly disagree = 1). Furthermore, all the measures evaluated the 'actions already taken' instead of 'intend to do' or 'identified as important to do'. In addition, the scope is limited to the micro-level of programme implementation, i.e., TVET institutions, and followed the terminology proposed by UNESCO (2021). The dependent variable is measured with the six-item scale shown in Table 3. The independent variables are measured with the 23-item scale shown in Table 4. The data point of the annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person applicable to each country is identified as per Asian Development Bank (2020, p.49).

Sample and method of data collection

We followed the definitions of ILO (2020, p. 60) and UNESCO-UNEVOC International Centre for TVET (2020, p. 7) for TVET staff. The sample consisted of TVET staff at the tertiary level in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields belonging to four broad categories - academic staff, academic support staff, technical staff, and administration. The Colombo Plan Staff College for Technician Education, located in the Philippines, allowed access to its member directory of around 2000 TVET staff who attended its in-country teacher training programmes during the last three years from the countries selected for the study (Table 1). We received 428 valid responses as shown in Table 1, which account for 21% response rate. The characteristics of respondents are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Characteristics of respondents

	%
GDP growth ¹ :	
Less than 4% (low GDP growth)	52.88
4% or more (high GDP growth)	47.12
Institution type:	
TVET teacher training/research institute	30.9
Polytechnic/TVET university	22.6
TVET college	46.5
Job type:	
Administration	47.4
Academic staff	38.6
Academic support staff	2.1
Technical staff	11.9
Highest education level:	
Doctorate	23.2

Master's degree	49.1
Bachelor's degree	17.9
Certificate/diploma/higher diploma	9.8
Sex:	
Female	24.9
Male	75.1
Age (in yrs):	
Mean	44.47
Std. deviation	9.059
Minimum	25.00
Maximum	68.00
Skewness	.064

Notes: ¹= refer to Table 1

Methods of data analysis

We tested the data for any differences by country using Wilks' Lambda statistic; the statistic showed non-existent of significant differences ($p > 0.05$), which is vital to proceed with the data analysis. The data were tested for reliability, validity, and factor structure as shown in Tables 3 to 5.

Table 3. Incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

	Factor loading
My institution has incorporated Industry 4.0 competencies into the existing curriculum	.894
My institution has incorporated Industry 4.0 competencies into the existing modules	.897
My institution has introduced additional modules to incorporate Industry 4.0 competencies into the existing programmes	.852
My institution has introduced programmes on digital skills to improve general digital literacy	.896
My institution uses digital/technology-based delivery in teaching and learning	.865
My institution has introduced lifelong learning courses to reskill and upskill TVET diplomates/graduates on Industry 4.0 competencies	.871
Eigenvalue	4.716
Total variance explained	78.594
Cronbach's Alpha	.904
Average variance extracted	.773
Construct reliability	.953

Table 4. Critical success factors

	F1: TVET staff capacity development	F2: TVET supportive culture	F3: TVET resources and public awareness
My institution facilitates staff to update subject-content knowledge in line with Industry 4.0 requirements	.894		
My institution facilitates staff to learn new pedagogies in line with Industry 4.0 requirements	.843		
My institution facilitates staff to learn new technological capabilities in line with Industry 4.0 requirements	.851		
My institution has introduced programmes on digital skills to improve the general digital literacy of staff	.908		
My institution recommends relevant training programs on Industry 4.0 competencies and technologies for staff	.897		
My institution encourages the use of digital/technology-based delivery in teaching and learning		.846	
My institution provides an understanding of competencies that should be developed for Industry 4.0		.892	
My institution provides guidance and support to address the needs of Industry 4.0		.896	
My institution provides opportunities for staff to share their experiences on Industry 4.0 competencies and technologies		.843	
My institution promotes close partnership with academia, industry, and other stakeholders for mutual learning to address the needs of Industry 4.0		.894	
My institution encourages us to learn from past experience and deal effectively with Industry 4.0 challenges		.833	
Overall, strategic goals of my institution are people-oriented, purpose-oriented, and process-oriented toward Industry 4.0		.889	
My institution hires new staff with capabilities in Industry 4.0 competencies and technologies			.890
My institution has adequate resources (equipment, computer hardware, software, and communication network) for on-line/digital delivery			.853

My institution conducts awareness programmes for the industry on the importance of Industry 4.0 competencies and technologies			.890
TVET regulating bodies in my country have consultants to advice on Industry 4.0 competency implementations			.899
My institution has consultants to advice on Industry 4.0 competency implementations			.901
Eigenvalue	5.972	4.302	4.013
Total variance explained	32.678	28.437	21.821
Cronbach's Alpha	.911	.904	.919
Average variance extracted	.773	.758	.786
Construct reliability	.944	.956	.948

Table 5. Correlations

	Mean	SE	1	2	3	4	5	6
1 TVET institution type ¹	-	-	-					
2 GDP growth ²	-	-	.183**	-				
3 TVET staff capacity development	5.14	.086	.268**	.118*	.879			
4 TVET supportive culture	5.20	.085	.257**	.090	.521**	.871		
5 TVET resources and public awareness	4.97	.088	.274**	.140*	.582**	.514**	.887	
6 Incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings	5.08	.084	.327**	.194*	.668**	.670**	.529**	.879

Notes: ¹ = Nominal (multicategorical, refer to Table 2); ² = Nominal (binary coded, refer to Table 2), SE = Standard error of the mean; Diagonal entries are square root of average variance extracted. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01 (2-tailed)

The research model shown in Figure 1 was tested with Hayes (2013) Process macro for SPSS. We used 5000 bootstrapped samples at bias-corrected 95% confidence intervals to test moderation effects. When coding moderators, the annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person (referred to as GDP growth) was binary coded (0 = Less than 4% [low GDP growth] and 1 = 4% or more [high GDP growth], refer to Table 2). Institution type was coded as a nominal variable having three categories (1 = TVET college, 2 = Polytechnic/TVET university, and 3 = TVET teacher training/research institute).

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Results of the correlation analysis together with descriptive statistics are shown in Table 5. Table 6 shows the results for the effect of staff capacity development on the dependent variable having both moderators. Statistics for the overall model involving IV1, moderators (institution type and GDP growth), interactions, and DV show that the overall model is significant (R-sq = .7740, p < 0.001). First, when considering the main effects, the effect of IV1 on DV is significant (t = 14.10, p < 0.001), where IV1 increases, DV also increases. This supports H1. When considering the effect of institution type on DV, the difference in DV between Polytechnic/TVET universities and TVET colleges is significant (W1, t = 2.68, p < 0.01); Polytechnic/TVET universities have implemented more in comparison to TVET colleges. Further, the difference in DV between TVET teacher training/research institutes and TVET colleges is significant (W2, t = 2.53, p < 0.05); TVET teacher training/research institutes have

implemented more in comparison to TVET colleges. When considering the effect of GDP growth on DV, the difference in DV between low GDP growth countries and high GDP growth countries is significant (GDP growth, $t = 3.03$, $p < 0.01$); high GDP growth countries have implemented more in comparison to low GDP growth countries.

Second, considering interaction effects, both interaction effects of institution type are not significant (Int_1, $p > 0.05$; Int_2, $p > 0.05$). In detail, although the impact of IV1 on DV in Polytechnic/TVET universities is considerably different (lower) from TVET colleges (Int_1, $t = -2.06$, $p > 0.05$) and the impact of IV1 on DV in TVET teacher training/research institutes is considerably different (lower) from TVET college (Int_2, $t = -1.98$, $p > 0.05$), these differences are not significant. These results do not support H4a. However, the interaction effect of GDP growth is significant (Int_3, $t = -3.09$, $p < 0.01$). Int_3 negatively moderates the relationship between IV1 and DV. That is, the impact of IV1 on DV in high GDP growth countries is considerably different (lower) from low GDP growth countries. This supports H5a.

Third, the results of the test of unconditional interaction effects show that the change in R-Sq due to the interaction of GDP growth (IV1*GDP growth, i.e., Int_3, $p < 0.05$) is significant. Although the change in R-Sq due to the interaction of institution type (IV1* Institution type, $p > 0.05$) is not significant, overall, the change in R-Sq due to both interactions is significant ($p < 0.01$). The conditional effects (or simple slopes) for IV1 to DV at a given level of institution type and GDP growth show that at all levels of institution type and GDP growth, IV1 significantly predicts DV. For example, IV1 predicting DV is significant at the institutional type 1 (i.e., TVET college) and GDP growth group 0 (i.e., low GDP growth countries). Likewise, IV1 predicting DV is significant at the institutional type 1 (i.e., TVET college) and GDP growth group 1 (i.e., high GDP growth countries), and so on. Finally, bootstrap confidence intervals (BootLLCI and BootULCI) for Int_3 do not include zero, where both have negative values. Hence, regression weight significantly differs from zero, fulfilling the condition for moderation (refer to Hayes, 2013). This supports H6.

Table 6. TVET staff capacity development on the incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

	R-sq	R2-chng	F	p
Overall effect on DV	.7740	-	93.4676	.0000
Highest order unconditional interaction effects:				
IV1*Institution type	-	.0073	3.0916	.0577
IV1*GDP growth	-	.0113	9.5341	.0023
Effect of both moderators	-	.0157	4.4116	.0050

Coefficients:						
Variable	B	SE	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
IV1	.9820	.0711	14.1006	.0000	.8618	1.1421
W1	.9628	.4343	2.6774	.0081	.3062	2.0194
W2	.9742	.4843	2.5280	.0123	.2690	2.1794
Int_1	-.1741	.0844	-2.0640	.0504	-.3406	.0077
Int_2	-.1698	.0857	-1.9816	.0590	-.3389	.0008
GDP growth	.9785	.3885	3.0332	.0028	.4121	1.9448
Int_3	-.2201	.0713	-3.0877	.0023	-.3607	-.0795

Conditional effects of IV1 at the values of moderators:							
Institution type	GDP growth	Effect	SE	t	P	LLCI	ULCI
1.0000	.0000	1.0020	.0711	14.1006	.0000	.8618	1.1421
1.0000	1.0000	.7819	.0502	15.5720	.0000	.6828	.8809
2.0000	.0000	.8278	.0852	9.7118	.0000	.6597	.9959
2.0000	1.0000	.6077	.0738	8.2403	.0000	.4623	.7532
3.0000	.0000	.8321	.0694	11.9910	.0000	.6952	.9690
3.0000	1.0000	.6120	.0809	7.5677	.0000	.4525	.7716

Bootstrap results for regression model parameters:					
	B	BootMean	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI
Int_3	-.2201	-.2189	.0874	-.3915	-.0466

Notes: DV = Incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings; IV1 = Staff capacity development; Reference category of institution type = TVET college, W1 = Polytechnic/TVET university vs TVET college; W2 = TVET teacher training/research institute vs TVET college; Int_1 = Product term of IV1 and W1; Int_2 = Product term of IV1 and W2; Int_3 = Product term of IV1 and GDP growth.

Table 7 shows the results for the effect of supportive culture on the dependent variables having both moderators. In succinct, the overall model is significant. First, the effect of IV2 on DV is significant. This supports H2. The difference in DV between Polytechnic/TVET universities and TVET colleges is significant; the difference in DV between TVET teacher training/research institutes and TVET colleges is significant. The difference in DV between low GDP growth countries and high GDP growth countries is not significant. Second, considering interaction effects, the impact of IV2 on DV in Polytechnic/TVET universities versus TVET colleges is not significant. However, the impact of IV2 on DV in TVET teacher training/research institutes versus TVET colleges is significant. Overall, the results partially support H4b. The interaction effect of GDP growth is not significant. This result does not support H5b. Third, the results of the test of unconditional interaction effects show that the change in R-Sq due to the interaction of institution type is significant ($p < 0.05$); the overall change in R-Sq

due to both interactions is significant ($p < 0.05$). At all levels of institution type and GDP growth, IV2 significantly predicts DV. Finally, bootstrap confidence intervals show that the condition for moderation is satisfied. This support H7.

Table 7. TVET supportive culture on the incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

	R-sq	R2-chng	F	p
Overall effect on DV	.7981	-	131.5714	.0000
Highest order unconditional interaction effects:				
IV2*Institution type	-	.0065	3.7658	.0246
IV2*GDP growth	-	.0022	2.5293	.1131
Effect of both moderators	-	.0076	2.9125	.0352

Coefficients:						
Variables	B	SE	T	p	LLCI	ULCI
IV2	.9385	.0522	17.9952	.0000	.8357	1.0412
W1	.8826	.3972	2.2222	.0272	.1001	1.6651
W2	.9849	.3941	3.2856	.0012	.5184	2.0714
Int_1	-.1310	.0765	-1.7134	.0880	-.2817	.0196
Int_2	-.1805	.0704	-2.5638	.0110	-.3191	-.0418
GDP growth	.4677	.3108	1.5047	.1338	-.1447	1.0800
Int_3	-.0924	.0581	-1.5904	.1131	-.2068	.0221

Conditional effects of IV2 at values of moderators:							
Institution type	GDP growth	Effect	SE	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
1.0000	.0000	.9385	.0522	17.9952	.0000	.8357	1.0412
1.0000	1.0000	.8461	.0472	17.9158	.0000	.7531	.9392
2.0000	.0000	.8075	.0724	11.1536	.0000	.6648	.9501
2.0000	1.0000	.7151	.0701	10.1959	.0000	.5769	.8533
3.0000	.0000	.7580	.0583	12.9973	.0000	.6431	.8730
3.0000	1.0000	.6657	.0688	9.6737	.0000	.5301	.8013

Bootstrap results for regression model parameters:					
	B	BootMean	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI
Int_2	-.1805	-.1819	.0731	-.3232	-.0383

Notes: DV = Incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings; IV2 = Supportive culture; Reference category of institution type = TVET college, W1 = Polytechnic/TVET university vs TVET college; W2 = TVET teacher training/research institute vs TVET college; Int_1 = Product term of IV2 and W1; Int_2 = Product term of IV2 and W2; Int_3 = Product term of IV2 and GDP growth.

Table 8 shows the results for the effect of availability of resources and public awareness on the dependent variable having both moderators. In succinct, the overall model is significant. First, the effect of IV3 on DV is significant. This supports H3. The difference in DV between Polytechnic/TVET universities and TVET colleges is significant; the difference in DV between TVET teacher training/research institutes and TVET colleges is significant; The difference in DV between high GDP growth countries and low GDP growth countries is not significant. Second, considering interaction

effects, the impact of IV3 on DV in Polytechnic/TVET universities versus TVET colleges is significant. However, the impact of IV3 on DV in TVET teacher training/research institutes versus TVET colleges is not significant. Overall, the results partially support H4c. Further, the interaction effect of GDP growth is not significant. This result does not support H5c. Third, the results of the test of unconditional interaction effects show that the change in R-Sq due to the interaction of institution type is significant ($p < 0.10$); the overall change in R-Sq due to both interactions is significant ($p < 0.10$). At all levels of institution type and GDP growth, IV3 significantly predicts DV. Finally, bootstrap confidence intervals show that the condition for moderation is satisfied. This supports H8.

Table 8. TVET resources and public awareness on the incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings

	R-sq	R2-chng	F	p
Overall effect on DV	.7286	-	73.2523	.0000
Highest order unconditional interaction effects:				
IV3*Institution type	-	.0080	2.8037	.0631
IV3*GDP growth	-	.0041	2.9041	.0900
Effect of both moderators	-	.0103	2.4249	.0670

Coefficients:						
Variables	B	SE	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
IV3	.9171	.0742	12.3648	.0000	.7708	1.0634
W1	.9725	.4521	3.0802	.0024	.5008	2.2842
W2	.9585	.5002	2.1160	.0356	.0718	2.0452
Int_1	-.2083	.0923	-2.2561	.0252	-.3905	-.0262
Int_2	-.1362	.0908	-1.5002	.1352	-.3153	.0429
GDP growth	.7265	.3949	1.8397	.0674	-.0524	1.5054
Int_3	-.1274	.0748	-1.7042	.0900	-.2749	.0201

Conditional effects of IV3 at values of moderators:							
Institution type	GDP growth	Effect	SE	t	P	LLCI	ULCI
1.0000	.0000	.9171	.0742	12.3648	.0000	.7708	1.0634
1.0000	1.0000	.7896	.0577	13.6967	.0000	.6759	.9034
2.0000	.0000	.7087	.0852	8.3226	.0000	.5408	.8767
2.0000	1.0000	.5813	.0827	7.0320	.0000	.4182	.7444
3.0000	.0000	.7809	.0746	10.4692	.0000	.6337	.9280
3.0000	1.0000	.6534	.0843	7.7528	.0000	.4872	.8197

Bootstrap results for regression model parameters:					
	B	BootMean	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI
Int_1	-.2083	-.2121	.1077	-.4209	-.0017

Notes: DV = Incorporation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings; IV3 = Resources and public awareness; Reference category of institution type = TVET college, W1 = Polytechnic/TVET university vs TVET college; W2 = TVET teacher training/research institute vs TVET college; Int_1 = Product term of IV3 and W1; Int_2 = Product term of IV3 and W2; Int_3 = Product term of IV3 and GDP growth.

Table 9. Summary of findings

Effect	Hypothesis	Result	Corresponding Table	Description
Staff capacity development -> DV	H1	Supported	Table 6	Staff capacity development enhances DV ($p < 0.001$)
Supportive culture -> DV	H2	Supported	Table 7	Supportive culture enhances DV ($p < 0.001$)
Resources and public awareness -> DV	H3	Supported	Table 8	Resources and public awareness enhance DV ($p < 0.001$)
Institution type -> DV	H4	Supported	Table 6	Institution type on DV is significant between Polytechnic/TVET universities and TVET colleges ($p < 0.01$) and between TVET teacher training/research institutes and TVET colleges ($p < 0.05$)
			Table 7	Institution type on DV is significant between Polytechnic/TVET universities and TVET colleges ($p < 0.05$) and between TVET teacher training/research institutes and TVET colleges ($p < 0.01$)
			Table 8	Institution type on DV is significant between Polytechnic/TVET universities and TVET colleges ($p < 0.05$) and between TVET teacher training/research institutes and TVET colleges ($p < 0.05$)
Staff capacity development -> DV having institution type as a moderator	H4a	Not supported	Table 6	Interaction effects of institution type is not significant at all levels
Supportive culture -> DV having institution type as a moderator	H4b	Partially supported	Table 7	Interaction effect in Polytechnic/TVET universities versus TVET colleges is not significant; TVET teacher training/research institutes versus TVET colleges is significant ($p < 0.05$)
Resources and public awareness -> DV having institution type as a moderator	H4c	Partially supported	Table 8	Interaction effect in Polytechnic/TVET universities versus TVET colleges is significant ($p < 0.05$); TVET teacher training/research institutes versus TVET colleges is not significant
GDP growth -> DV	H5	Partially supported	Table 6	GDP growth is significant ($p < 0.01$) between low GDP growth countries and high GDP growth countries
			Table 7	GDP growth is not significant ($p > 0.05$) between low GDP growth countries and high GDP growth countries
			Table 8	GDP growth is not significant ($p > 0.05$) between low GDP growth countries and high GDP growth countries
Staff capacity development -> DV having GDP growth as a moderator	H5a	Supported	Table 6	Interaction effects of GDP growth is significant ($p < 0.01$)
Supportive culture -> DV having GDP growth as a moderator	H5b	Not supported	Table 7	Interaction effect of GDP growth is not significant
Resources and public awareness -> DV having GDP growth as a moderator	H5c	Not supported	Table 8	Interaction effect of GDP growth is not significant
Model 1 - Staff capacity development on DV having both institution type and GDP growth as moderators	H6	Supported	Table 6	ΔR^2 due to the interaction of GDP growth is significant ($p < 0.05$) ΔR^2 due to the interaction of institution type is not significant ΔR^2 due to both interactions is significant ($p < 0.01$) At all levels of institution type and GDP growth, staff capacity development significantly predicts DV ($p < 0.001$ for all levels)
Model 2 - Supportive culture on DV having both institution type and GDP growth as moderators	H7	Supported	Table 7	ΔR^2 due to the interaction of institution type is significant ($p < 0.05$) ΔR^2 due to the interaction of GDP growth is not significant ΔR^2 due to both interactions is significant ($p < 0.05$) At all levels of institution type and GDP growth, supportive culture significantly predicts DV ($p < 0.001$ for all levels)
Model 3 - Resources and public awareness on DV having both institution type and GDP growth as moderators	H8	Supported	Table 8	ΔR^2 due to the interaction of institution type is significant ($p < 0.10$) ΔR^2 due to the interaction of GDP growth is not significant ΔR^2 due to both interactions is significant ($p < 0.10$) At all levels of institution type and GDP growth, resources and public awareness significantly predicts DV ($p < 0.001$ for all levels)

IMPLICATIONS OF THE FINDINGS

The study found that the three critical success factors significantly positively predict the implementation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings. It was also found that institution type and annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person boost the relationship. Of the three institution types, TVET colleges were in a weaker position compared to the other two institution types (Table 9).

Concerning the annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person, countries with high growth rates have implemented more in comparison to countries with low growth rates. The findings have important implications for the literature, practice, and policymaking across countries, regions, and continents.

With regard to the theoretical contributions, first, whilst there is a widespread agreement that Industry 4.0 technologies are making a profound impact on the agenda of education, the literature such as Spöttl and Windelband (2021) and Schröder (2019) suggest that limited research attention has been paid so far to investigate the success factors behind the implementation of Industry 4.0 competencies into higher education programmes. Therefore, our research makes an invaluable contribution to the literature at the regional or even global level.

Second, the World Bank (The World Bank Group, 2021) and UNESCO (2021) have propagated the need to establish almost uniform TVET systems within and across countries. Still, there can be differences due to certain characteristics within countries. We investigated two of such characteristics - TVET institution type and annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person. We found that institution type has a direct effect on the implementation of Industry 4.0 competencies (DV) as well as it is an important moderator which can make a significant impact on the variables of interest (IVs) (Table 9). Regarding the annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person, when a country is behind in economic development and poor in maintaining labour markets, there could be limited job openings requiring middle-level technical expertise with attractive labour market rewards. This suggests the importance of assessing the impact of annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person. We have not found any previous studies that tried to integrate such country context variables in cross-country investigations. Our proposition was that when a country's annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person is higher, that country could place a higher weight on its TVET system for lower and middle-level job creation, thereby assisting in addressing poverty and unemployment in the country. The findings provide evidence to suggest that the annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person affects the implementation of Industry 4.0 competencies (DV) and operates as an important moderator (Table 9). Hence, we believe that our incorporation of this indicator as a moderator would provide novel insight and make valuable contributions to the literature.

Third, since the sample covered 15 countries, there is much potential to generalise the findings across countries. In this regard, the importance of generalisability across countries have been constantly pronounced in the literature on TVET (e.g., Schröder, 2019; The World Bank Group, 2021). Our research provides empirical findings at a critical time in research on TVET with the dawn of Industry 4.0. The critical success factors we have identified in the Indo-Pacific region can be extended beyond this region. Researchers from other regions and continents can use the measures developed by us in future investigations for comparative purposes. Therefore, our research makes invaluable contributions to the literature.

We can identify several implications for practice. First, the findings showed the importance of staff capacity development. At the institution level, the promotion of acquiring requisite competencies

(new subject content knowledge, technology use, and pedagogies), assistance by providing self-learning options, and support by recommending development programmes are important. In addition, the responsibility of staff capacity development cannot be regarded as solely lies with TVET institutions. Staff should also take responsibility for their own professional development and staying relevant. They should be passionate as well as should have self-determination and a sense of ownership to succeed and build their careers.

Second, the findings imply that as a part of supporting culture, TVET institutions must consider promoting staff exchange programmes with industry to keep staff abreast of technological developments in work processes. Further, providing support through recommendations, encouragement, guidance, and the communities of practice to update staff competencies – subject content knowledge, use of digital platforms and tools, and pedagogical. The findings suggest the need for initiatives for constant dialogue between academia, industry, and other stakeholders for mutual learning to address the requisites of Industry 4.0 for curriculum development, staff capacity building, and student apprenticeship/internship training.

Third, the findings suggest that TVET institutions' autonomy and capacity to hire new staff with Industry 4.0 competencies and technologies, acquisition of appropriate digital infrastructure to develop a conducive teaching and learning environment and come into agreements/partnerships with digital service providers such as broadband lead to successful implementation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings. In this regard, previous research highlighted the importance of financing TVET programmes (e.g., Gonçalves, 2019; McGrath et al. 2020; Oketch 2016; The World Bank Group, 2021). In addition, the findings imply that TVET institutions must maintain a close connection with the public (mainly industrial sectors as a whole) to publicise the value of implementing Industry 4.0 technologies at workplaces.

The study has implications for policy making. What, when and how to transform economies and societies along with Industry 4.0 should ingest a major chunk of the national agenda of all countries. Our findings of the two moderators suggest some implications for policymaking. First, it is the ultimate responsibility of the State to make appropriate policy decisions to provide all types of TVET institutions with opportunities for inclusive growth. A State's policies and initiatives for the creation of a multi-stakeholder collaboration system for TVET, for example, may reduce disparities at the institution level and may boost institutions' capacity to implement Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings. Second, the extent of preparedness of a country to take advantage of Industry 4.0 could be depicted by national-level economic indicators, like, the annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person. TVET institutions are influenced by the character of economic conditions. The findings showed that the annual growth rate of real GDP per employed person could operate as a moderating factor and affect the implementation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings. This suggests that a country's policies and actions on employment generation, technological upgrading and innovation will

bring about economic transformations and help to yield higher levels of productivity; with these transformations, changes to institutions' programme offerings are highly likely.

CONCLUSION

Given the accelerating speed of changes occurring due to Industry 4.0, the existence of research studies on the response of higher education in programme offerings is disproportionately small worldwide. In response to this backdrop, we questioned what are the critical success factors that support the implementation of Industry 4.0 competencies into TVET programme offerings. Our study identified critical success factors surrounding incorporating competencies into programme offerings, adopting appropriate teaching and learning practices, and staff capacity building in the context of Industry 4.0. The findings also showed the role of two moderators that can boost the implementation of Industry 4.0 competencies into programme offerings.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

First, our scope was limited to TVET institutions at the tertiary level in STEM fields. It is imperative that enormous conditions intermingled together may influence successful implementations. Still, we believe our findings inspire future researchers to meaningfully expand the depth and breadth of future investigations. Regarding future research, the level of TVET system understudy can be broadened to include macro or meso-levels. Further, the findings on moderators imply that a country's policies could enhance the type of programmes offered and the way these are delivered. Furthermore, the present study was limited to 15 countries in Indo-Pacific. However, TVET is of interest to all countries across regions/continents. The method we have adopted and measures we have developed can be tested across countries to increase the scholarly contribution to TVET field.

References

- Bai, B., & Paryono, B. (2019). *Vocational education and training in ASEAN member states. Perspectives on rethinking and reforming education*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-6617-8_7
- Alade, K., & Windapo, A. (2020). 4IR leadership effectiveness and practical implications for construction business organisations. In Aigbavboa, C. & Thwala, W. (Eds.) *The Construction Industry in the Fourth Industrial Revolution*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-26528-1_7
- Amegah, A. (2023). Business without social responsibility is business without morality: Employer engagement in upper secondary technical and vocational education and training schools in Ghana. *Journal of Vocational Education & Training*, 75(2), 391-415. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13636820.2021.1879904>
- Asian Development Bank. (2020). *Key indicators for Asia and the Pacific 2020* (51st Edition). Manila, Philippines: Asian Development Bank. <https://dx.doi.org/10.22617/FLS200250-3>, CC-BY 3.0 IGO
- Bhattacharyya, S., & Mitra, A. (2020). Fourth industrial revolution and India's 'employment problem'. *International Journal of Social Economics*. 47(7), 851-866. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSE-09-2019-0540>

- Bosler, C., Daly, M.C., Fernald, J.G., & Hobijn, B. (2019). The outlook for U.S. labor-quality growth. Chapter 3 in Hulten, C.R., & Ramey, V.A. (eds), *Education, Skills, and Technical Change: Implications for Future U.S. GDP Growth*, 61-110, Cambridge, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research. Available at: <https://www.nber.org/papers/w22555> (Retrieved 20 June 2024)
- Butt, R., Siddiqui, H., Soomro, R.A., & Asad, M.M. (2020). Integration of industrial revolution 4.0 and IOTs in academia: A state-of-the-art review on the concept of Education 4.0 in Pakistan. *Interactive Technology and Smart Education*, 17(4), 337-354. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/ITSE-02-2020-0022>
- Gonçalves, C.U. (2019). *Financing TVET: A comparative analysis in six Asian countries*. France: Agence Française de Développement (AFD). Available at <https://www.afd.fr/en/ressources/financing-tvet-comparative-analysis-six-asian-countries> (Accessed 27 April 2023).
- Hayes, A.F. (2013). *Introduction to mediation, moderation, and conditional process analysis*. New York, NY: The Guilford Press.
- Holler, S., Brändle, M., & Zinn, B. (2023). How do South African TVET lecturers rate their digital competencies, and what is their need for training for a digital transformation in the South African TVET sector? *Journal of Vocational, Adult and Continuing Education and Training*, 6(1), 25. <https://doi.org/10.14426/jovacet.v6i1.314>
- ILO (2020). *The digitization of TVET and skills systems*. Geneva: ILO. Available at: https://www.ilo.org/skills/areas/skills-policies-and-systems/WCMS_752213/lang-en/index.htm (Retrieved 25 April 2023)
- Jabarullah, N.H., & Hussain, H.I. (2019). The effectiveness of problem-based learning in technical and vocational education in Malaysia. *Education + Training*, 61(5), 552-567. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ET-06-2018-0129>
- Jongen, E.L.W. (2004). *Future GDP growth in Slovenia: Looking for room for improvement*. Institute for Economic Research. Available at: <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=c575fb40d14ede5464f9889ce08071dbbf79f15b> (Retrieved 20 June 2024)
- Mahdum, M., Hadriana, H., & Safriyanti, M. (2019). Exploring teacher perceptions and motivations to ICT use in learning activities in Indonesia. *Journal of Information Technology Education: Research*, 18, 293-317. <https://doi.org/10.28945/4366>
- Marattin, L., & Salotti, S. (2011). Productivity and per capita GDP growth: The role of the forgotten factors. *Economic Modelling*, 28(3), 1219-1225. Available at: https://mp.ra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/29294/1/MPRA_paper_29294.pdf (Retrieved 20 June 2024)
- Marzuki, M.A.B., Yusof, R., Yusof, R., & Musa, K. (2022). Evaluating the TVET financial allocation based on the polytechnics and community colleges students' enrolment: A preliminary analysis. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 11(2), 1267-1284. <http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJARPED/v11-i2/13911>
- McGrath, S., Ramsarup, P., Zeelen, J., Wedekind, V., Allais, S., Lotz-Sisitka, H., Monk, D., Openjuru, G., & Russon, J.-A. (2020). Vocational education and training for African development: A literature review. *Journal of Vocational Education & Training*, 72(4), 465-487. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13636820.2019.1679969>.
- Millar, C., Groth, O., & Mahon, J. (2018). Management innovation in a VUCA world: Challenges and recommendations. *California Management Review*, 61(1), 5-14. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0008125618805111>
- Oketch, M. (2016). Financing higher education in Sub-Saharan Africa: Some reflections and implications for sustainable development. *Higher Education*, 72(4), 525-539. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-016-0044-6>.
- Persson, B., & Hermelin, B. (2018). Mobilising for change in vocational education and training in Sweden - A case study of the 'Technical College' scheme. *Journal of Vocational Education & Training*, 70(3), 476-496. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13636820.2018.1443971>
- Pima, J.M (2019). Factors that motivate teachers to use ICT in teaching: A case of Kaliua District secondary schools in Tanzania. *International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology*, 15(1), 1-11. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1214272>

- Schröder, T. (2019). A regional approach for the development of TVET systems in the light of the 4th industrial revolution: The regional association of vocational and technical education in Asia. *International Journal of Training Research*, 17(S1), 83-95. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14480220.2019.1629728>
- Spöttl, G., & Windelband, L. (2021). The 4th industrial revolution - its impact on vocational skills. *Journal of Education and Work*, 34(1), 29-52. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13639080.2020.1858230>
- The United Nations. (n.d.). *Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth*. The United Nations. Available at: <https://www.globalgoals.org/goals/8-decent-work-and-economic-growth/> (Retrieved 27 April 2023).
- The World Bank Group (2021). *Unleashing the power of educational technology in TVET systems*. Washington DC: The World Bank Group. Available at: <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/61714f214ed04bcd6e9623ad0e215897-0400012021/related/EdTech-Report-FIN2-web.pdf> (Retrieved 27 April 2023)
- TVET Academy (2021). *Digitalization and TVET*. Magdeburg, Germany: Academy for International Cooperation (GIZ). Available at: <https://www.giz.de/akademie/de/downloads/Conference-Digitalization-documentation.pdf> (Retrieved 28 April 2023)
- UNESCO-UNEVOC International Centre for TVET (2020). *UNESCO-UNEVOC study on the trends shaping the future of TVET teaching*. Bonn, Germany: UNESCO-UNEVOC. Available at: https://unevoc.unesco.org/pub/trendsmapping_futureoftvetteaching.pdf (Retrieved 27 April 2023)
- UNESCO. (2021). *New qualifications and competencies for future-oriented TVET – Volume 3: TVET delivery – Providing innovative solutions*. Bonn, Germany: UNESCO-UNEVOC International Centre for Technical and Vocational Education and Training, UNESCO.
- World Economic Forum (2016). *The future of jobs: Employment, skills, and workforce strategy for the fourth industrial revolution*. Geneva: World Economic Forum. Available at: https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Future_of_Jobs.pdf (Retrieved 28 April 2023)
- Yaakob, H. (2017). Technical and Vocational Education & Training (TVET) Institutions towards statutory body: Case study of Malaysian Polytechnic. *Advanced Journal of Technical and Vocational Education*, 1(2), 7-13, <http://dx.doi.org/10.26666/rmp.ajtve.2017.2.2>